

ASSESSING THE HABITAT FRAGMENTATION OF SOCIOECONOMICALLY
IMPORTANT TREE SPECIES IN COSTA RICA

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In
Geography: Resource Management and Environmental Planning

by

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San Francisco, California

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CERTIFICATION OF APPROVAL

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ASSESSING THE HABITAT FRAGMENTATION OF SOCIOECONOMICALLY IMPORTANT TREE SPECIES IN COSTA RICA

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The suitable habitat of 29 timber species native to Costa Rica was assessed using landscape analysis and habitat models. The modeling was done using Maxent, 20 environmental layers and herbarium localities. GIS layers of forest cover and protected areas of the country were used to quantify the amount of suitable habitat covered by forest inside and outside the protected areas. The resulting layers were used to address the reduction of suitable habitat of each species due to deforestation, their degree of protection and the fragmentation of the remaining unprotected habitat.

The risk of the species was measured using the IUCN Red List methodology and values given by gap analysis previously done in Costa Rica. The results show that the most threatened species are adequately protected and that three of the five most fragmented species outside the protected areas of the country are located in the same region, the Osa Peninsula. This project gives new inputs for the management of the Costa Rican forests, showing species and areas where resources should be focused.

I certify that the Abstract is a correct representation of the content of this thesis.

Barbara A. Holzman, Ph.D.

Date

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INTRODUCTION

During the last centuries, the impact of human population growth has reduced natural habitat throughout the world quite rapidly. Species have disappeared faster than being described or studied by biologists, and the negative effects of this destruction have evidently affected human development (Diamond 2004). With this in mind, protection and conservation of natural habitats and resources have acquired an important role in the persistence of biological diversity and the well-being of human societies due to the ecosystem services they provide. The selection of important areas and species for conservation has become a key necessity, and it has been an active research topic during the last decades.

Due to their high biodiversity and unsustainable economic practices, developing countries in the tropics have been affected by habitat destruction to a higher degree than wealthier and more temperate countries. Countries in Central America have addressed this issue in different ways, and Costa Rica has relied primarily on the creation of protected areas throughout their remaining forest patches for most of the second half of the 20th century. The government and nongovernmental associations (NGOs) in this Central American country have

helped in guiding the creation of these protected areas by developing studies involving forest mapping and gap analyses. In the late 1990s, in an effort to protect several timber species from overexploitation, the Costa Rican government also implemented a law which prohibits forest cover change and banned the logging of a group of 18 species (Jiménez-Madrigal 1998). This action was driven by the publication of a book regarding endangered timber species and several articles in Costa Rican newspapers (Jiménez-Madrigal 1998). Although the banning of these species was widely accepted by the public, the choice of species was highly controversial and heavily contested by the forestry industry and certain academic sectors. The principal critique was the selection of species based solely on expert knowledge guided by personal experience in the field, including many species with no quantitative data demonstrating their actual risk.

Currently, several new techniques have become available to assess the destruction of habitats and the risk of the species. Species distribution models (SMDs) used with data available at natural history museums, geographic information systems (GIS) and remotely sensed data have become important tools for researchers, managers and politicians in implementing conservation practices in different countries throughout the world. In Latin America, most of the research involving these techniques has been carried out in Mexico (Cayuela *et*

al. 2009), with almost no research published in the international journals written in Central America.

In the quest for an adequate method to assess the risk of extinction of species, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) published its well-known Red Book in 2001, a document considered one of the most widespread and adequate methodologies available to date (de Grammont & Cuaron 2006). It uses different criteria to categorize the degree of endangerment of the species, including reduction of the species' range and its current size. Although the Red Book methodology was published recently, it was not designed for the new techniques mentioned above. In order to apply the new techniques, a group of Mexican researchers recently adapted the Red Book methodology to SDMs and GIS (Arroyo *et al.* 2009).

In an effort to support and guide adequate and sustainable management of the Costa Rican forests and quantify the degree of endangerment to different timber species in Costa Rica, this project relied on all of the aforementioned techniques to answer three important questions:

1. How much of the original habitat of a group of timber species has been reduced by land-use / land-cover change?

2. How much of their remaining habitat is included in the protected areas?
3. How fragmented is the unprotected habitat?

These questions were approached using SDMs as a proxy of the species' range while the species banned were taken as a baseline to assess the threat of the other species and the effect of their protection. These three questions are intimately related with the management of the Costa Rican forests and, as previously stated, represent the first attempt in the country to address conservation and management issues through SDMs and GIS.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review is divided into three main topics closely related with the objectives of this project: habitat fragmentation and its effects on biodiversity, species distribution modeling, and land-use / land-cover change (LULCC) in Costa Rica. The first part focuses on the research that has addressed the effects of forest fragmentation on tropical biodiversity, with emphasis on studies related to tree species. The second part describes some basic concepts and methods that are currently used in species distribution modeling. Finally, the third part gives some insights of research carried out in Costa Rica addressing deforestation, its driving forces and the effectiveness of protected areas in safeguarding the biodiversity of the country.

Habitat fragmentation

Habitat fragmentation is a landscape process that involves loss of habitat and change in its spatial configuration (Fahrig 2003). The fragmentation process implies a subdivision of a formerly contiguous landscape into smaller fragments or patches, reducing continuity and interfering with species dispersal and migration. Habitat fragmentation is considered an important threat to biodiversity and one of the most important causes of species extinction (Simberloff 1986). In

the tropics, due to agriculture, grazing and settlement, it is estimated that forest cover has been reduced to approximately half of its potential extent and fragmented habitats have become a common characteristic of the landscape (Laurance & Bierregaard 1997; Roper & Roberts 1999)

Most of the research related to tropical forest fragmentation has been carried out by the Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute in the Biological Dynamics of Forest Fragments Project of the Brazilian Amazon (Laurance *et al.* 1998, 2003, 2006, 2000). These studies have identified that the area of the fragments, their edge, and their spatial and temporal isolation are important characteristics of fragmented landscapes affecting the species composition and their survival. These findings have been supported by similar studies carried out in other tropical areas of the world (Hill & Curran 2003; Metzger 2000; Jacinto Tabanez & Viana 2000).

Habitat fragmentation has a negative effect on the survival of populations, principally due to the decrease in population size and the increase of spatial isolation between populations (Gilpin 1991). In trees, the reduction of the number of reproductive individuals represents a decrease in the number of pollen donors and in the quantity of pollen dispersed. This, in conjunction with a decline in animal vectors of pollen and seed dispersal, may increase the level of

inbreeding, reduce the genetic variability and increase interpopulation genetic divergence (Nason & Hamrick 1997; Young, Boyle, & Brown 1996; Turner 1996; Sork & Smouse 2006). In the short term, this can reduce both individual fitness and remnant population viability and, in the long term, may limit the ability of the species to adapt to changes in selection pressures and drive them to extinction (Young *et al.* 1996).

Empirical research has investigated in different ways the possible effects that habitat fragmentation has in the survival of trees. In the tropics, this research has focused on pollination intensity and seed production (Murcia 1996), flowering phenology (Fuchs, Lobo, & Quesada 2003), population genetic structure (Aldrich & Hamrick 1998), seedling abundance (Benitez-Malvido 1998) and overall reproductive success (Cascante *et al.* 2002; Quesada *et al.* 2004). Their results show that tropical tree species are especially vulnerable to habitat fragmentation due to their low densities, reduced pollination activity, self-incompatibility systems and high rates of outbreeding.

Concerning habitat fragmentation and species richness, Metzger (2000) was able to identify that tropical shade-tolerant trees are affected by the fragmentation process in a higher degree than shade-intolerant species. In his study Metzger shows that the number of shade-tolerant species found in the

fragmented forest is positively correlated with the area of the fragment and its connectivity with other fragments. Laurance *et al.* (2006, 1998) and Ferreira & Laurance (1997) found that at the edges of forest fragments, successional species increase in abundance due to an elevated mortality of the species that originally inhabited the area. The causes of this tree mortality have been associated with changes in the microclimate around the fragments, especially by fluxes of solar radiation, changes in the wind patterns and in the local water regime (Saunders, Hobbs, & Margules 1991; Ferreira & Laurance 1997). Due to the relationship between area and edge, smaller patches are more affected by edge effects than larger ones (Laurance, Vasconcelos, & Lovejoy 2000).

Several methods have been employed to quantify habitat fragmentation, an effort mainly driven by the development of a software package called Fragstats (McGarigal *et al.* 2002). Researchers have used more than 40 different metrics to assess fragmentation, ranging from simple area calculations to higher complexity indices (McGarigal & Cushman 2002; Haines-Young & Chopping 1996). Despite this large number of metrics, most of them are highly correlated and related with four main characteristics of the landscape: habitat area, number of habitat patches, size of the patches and their isolation (Fahrig 2003; Haines-Young & Chopping 1996). Some of these metrics have also been criticized due to their lack of clear ecological meaning (Li & Wu 2004; Gustafson 1998). Li &

Wu (2004) suggest that complex metrics should be avoided unless there is a clear understanding of their ecological relevance, preferring simpler metrics with empirical evidence of their significance in the ecology of the studied species.

With respect to landscape metrics and their effects on biodiversity, research has identified the independent effects of reduction of habitat and landscape configuration (Fahrig 1997, 2002). Results show that the total area of habitat is the most important factor to determine persistence of a species in a landscape, while habitat configuration effects become apparent only when the amount of habitat is low (Fahrig 1997, 2002, 2003; Lindenmayer *et al.* 2008). Theoretical studies have identified that the threshold where habitat configuration is more important than its total area occurs when the remaining habitat is between 20 and 30 percent of the original habitat, but there is still no empirical evidence of its existence (Fahrig 2003).

Species Distribution Models

Species distribution models (SDMs) have become critical in conservation planning during the last twenty years. These models are based on empirical associations between environmental variables and known species occurrence. They are used to identify the environmental conditions necessary for populations

of certain species to survive. SDMs are divided into two groups: those that use presence-only data, and those that use both presence and absence data.

SDMs are based on two inputs, an algorithm or statistical model that finds the relationship between these inputs, and a resulting map showing the geographic distribution of the species under study. The inputs consist of the environmental variables (i.e. temperature and precipitation) that are predictors in defining the species distribution and the locations where the species has been observed, and in the case of presence-absence models, where it is also known to be absent.

SDMs rely on the concept of the ecological niche originally proposed by Hutchinson (1957). He stated that the niche can be seen as an n-dimensional hypervolume in which every point corresponds to a state of the environment that permits a species to exist indefinitely. The simplest interpretation of this view is that a species occurs in all the places where conditions are suitable but it never occurs where conditions are unsuitable, a concept that is also referred to as the “fundamental” niche. The “ecological” niche is a function of the physiological performance and ecosystem constraints of each species (Guisan & Zimmermann 2000) and a critical determinant of its geographic distribution (Peterson 2001).

The “realized” niche is a space inside the fundamental niche that includes the biotic interaction and geographic barriers of a species (Phillips, Anderson, & Schapire 2006). According to Peterson (2003), four historical effects have been identified as causes that lead to differences between fundamental and realized niches:

- Limited dispersal: this characteristic keeps a species from encountering other suitable areas, particularly when these areas are separate from the species’ present distribution.
- Speciation: allopatric speciation produces sister species in suitable areas previously inhabited by the ancestral species.
- Extinction: populations of the species may previously have existed in an area but have gone extinct.
- Competition: intraspecific competition that may limit the species geographic distribution.

As a consequence of these four effects, suitable habitat almost always exists outside of the species’ present geographic distribution, and it should be considered when using the predicted distribution maps.

A general simplification of the relationships between SDMs, fundamental and realized niches is that SDMs quantify the realized niche of the species, while

only mechanistic models, or niche-based models based on *ex situ* data can approach the fundamental niche (Guisan & Thuiller 2005). This idea is still debated, as some authors state that SDMs provide an approximation to the species fundamental niche (Soberon & Peterson 2005). Other authors argue that the models are a spatial representation of the realized niche (Guisan & Zimmermann 2000; Pearson, Dawson, & Liu 2004). Due to these differences, the products of SDMs have also been called *potential geographic distributions* (Araujo & Guisan 2006) or *habitat suitability maps* (Kremen *et al.* 2008).

SDMs are based on two basic assumptions: the degree to which the species is at equilibrium with the current environmental conditions, and the extent to which observed occurrence records provide a sample of the environmental space occupied by the species. Generally, a species is at equilibrium when it occurs in all suitable areas, but is absent from all unsuitable areas. This situation depends both on biotic interactions and dispersal ability. Research indicates that organisms with higher dispersal ability are likely closer to equilibrium than organisms with lower dispersal ability (Araujo & Pearson 2005).

Guisan & Thuiller (2005) introduced the concept of *pseudo-equilibrium* with the environment. They state that as in SDMs both species and environmental data are sampled during a limited period of time and space, models created

using these values can only reflect a snapshot view of the expected relationship. This should be taken into consideration when modeling invasive species distributions, as these species are not in equilibrium with the environment in the invaded range (Peterson 2003). Pulliam (2000) raised another point related with the equilibrium assumptions. He notes various examples of species that are absent from suitable habitats and present in unsuitable habitats. The first case occurs in meta-population dynamics, when local extinctions in suitable habitat are common. Examples of the second are related to source-sink dynamics and are common in migratory species.

The second assumption mentioned above is related to the number of samples used as inputs in the modeling process. In cases where very few occurrence records are available, it is unlikely that they will provide sufficient samples of the full range of environmental conditions occupied by the species to be modeled (Peterson 2003). Currently, the largest amount of data available for SDMs comes from natural history museums. In many cases these data are incomplete and biased in relation to the true spatial or environmental distribution of the species (Araujo & Guisan 2006). The localities from these sources are often not based on any pre-established sampling methodologies and are highly correlated with the nearby presence of towns, roads and rivers. Phillips *et al.* (2009) and VanDerWal *et al.* (2009) recently studied this issue and its effects on

SDMs. Using modeling software called Maxent, Phillips *et al.* (2009) showed that it is possible to reduce the influence of this sample selection bias and improve the predictive performance of the SDMs by changing the way the algorithm chooses the samples of the study area that will create the model. Instead of using random samples of the environmental conditions of the study area (also called background data) Phillips *et al.* (2009) used sample data that reflects the same bias as the occurrence data. They called this type of sampling a target-group background, which uses samples from other locations taken from natural history museums collections. Van DerWal *et al.* (2009) noted differences in the performance of the models depending on the extent of the study area, and concluded that it is important to consider the extent where the sample data are taken, especially when modeling across different regions or times.

Hernandez *et al.* (2006) and Wisz *et al.* (2008) studied the effects of sample size. Both studies found differences in the performance of different models in relation to the number of different localities used. Their results show that for presence-only modeling algorithms, the software Maxent (Phillips *et al.* 2006) performed better than the others. Hernandez *et al.* (2006) and Pearson *et al.* (2007) noted that Maxent produces useful results with sample sizes as small as five different localities.

Other errors or bias in the inputs of the modeling process should also be considered. Phillips *et al.* (2006) mention the following possible bias: the location of the occurrence records may be incorrect due to transcription errors, the lack of sufficient geographic detail (especially in older records), and misidentification of the species. Errors in the environmental variables may come from data manipulation, inaccuracies in the climatic models used to generate the climatic variables, and interpolation of low-resolution data.

Several studies addressed the evaluation of SDMs (Fielding & Bell 1997; Liu *et al.* 2005; Araujo & Guisan 2006; Raes & Steege 2007; Jiménez-Valverde & Lobo 2007; Lobo, Jiménez-Valverde, & Real 2008). SDMs are usually evaluated by comparing the predicted maps with a group of test data. The test data can be a subsample of the original dataset or, in the best case, independent data. According to a recent literature review done by Cayuela *et al.* (2009), the majority of research that used SDMs evaluated the models by creating subsamples of the original dataset. The way in which these subsamples are chosen can involve different sampling techniques, for example, dividing the dataset into two groups and using one to create the model and the other to test it. Such kind of sampling can be done several times by sampling randomly with replacement (bootstrapping) or by sampling without replacement, creating a distribution of the validation value where statistics can be calculated (Fielding & Bell 1997).

Different validation values or statistics are used to assess the performance of SDMs. According to the output of the models these methods are divided into threshold-dependent and independent. Threshold-dependent methods are applied when the model gives a binary prediction (presence-absence) or when a threshold value is applied to the probability values to generate a presence-absence map. The performance of these models is assessed using a contingency table (also known as a confusion matrix) and by calculating all the common statistics associated with these kinds of data (e.g. accuracy, Kappa). Due to the lack of known absences in presence-only models, this method is not recommended unless it is tested for statistical significance. Such testing is done by identifying the proportion of observed occurrences correctly predicted (also known as sensitivity) using a binomial test or chi-square test (Anderson, Gomez-Laverde, & Peterson 2002; Pearson *et al.* 2007).

Threshold-independent assessments are the most common evaluation method for SDMs that produce maps of probabilities. The statistic used is called the Area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve, a method originally developed in signal processing and commonly used in clinical medicine (Fielding & Bell 1997). The curve is created by plotting the sensitivity values against the proportion of observed absences incorrectly predicted (also called “1 – specificity”) for the entire range of possible thresholds. The area under the curve

(AUC) represents the probability of the model to discriminate between presence and absence records. The AUC and its meaning in SMDs created using presence-only data is discussed later in the methodology section of this project.

SDMs have been used to address important questions in fields as diverse as ecology, biogeography, evolution, conservation biology and climate change (Araujo & Guisan 2006). Cayuela *et al.* (2009) conducted the most up-to-date review of research that incorporated SDMs. The 123 peer-reviewed articles they found were divided into eight different research scopes (biodiversity mapping, conservation prioritization, biogeography, autoecology, climate change, biological invasions, species conservation, and methodological) and the two biomes where the research was done (temperate and tropical). Their study shows that most of the published articles focus on methodological questions, followed by species conservation, biological invasions and climate change respectively. In relation to the main scope of this thesis project, which falls between species conservation and biodiversity mapping, twenty five articles addressed species conservation questions in the temperate biome while only five were done in the tropics (Mexico, Namibia, India and Ecuador). In relation to biodiversity mapping, two articles were done in the tropics (Mexico and Burkina Faso) and only one in the temperate biome.

Land-use and land-cover change in Costa Rica

The first study that quantified the forest extent in Costa Rica was carried out between 1955 and 1966. The project was done using aerial photographs and field observations taken by the US Defense Mapping Agency and produced a set of 1:250,000 scale maps of forested / non-forested areas (Joyce 2006). During 1979, the Costa Rican Meteorological Institute (IMN) created a set of 1:100,000 scale forest maps using black-and-white prints of images acquired by the Landsat Multispectral Scanner (Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2003). Later, due to the wide availability of data from the Landsat Program, several studies were done in specific regions of the country, but it was not until the year 2000 when a forest map was created for the entire country (Sánchez-Azofeifa, Harriss, & Skole 2001). This map facilitated a large amount of ecological research in different areas of Costa Rica; for example, in the dry forests of the northwest of the country, studies were carried out by the Earth Observation Systems Laboratory of the University of Alberta and the Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica (e.g. Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2003; Kalacska *et al.* 2004; Arroyo-Mora, Sánchez-Azofeifa, Kalacska, *et al.* 2005) and in the countryside of the southwestern mountains of Costa Rica by the Center for Conservation Biology at Stanford University and the Organization for Tropical Studies (e.g. Daily, Ehrlich, & Sánchez-Azofeifa 2001; Daily *et al.* 2003; Brosi *et al.* 2007). This forest map was

also used by governmental institutions to address conservation issues such as selecting areas to devote for payments for ecosystem services and issuing timber extraction permits.

The usefulness of this forest map encouraged the Costa Rican Government to fund a new mapping project in 2005. The resulting map used a mix of data sources to identify 16 different land-use / land-cover categories, including old-growth forest and secondary growth. Although it was not publicly available until 2007, it has already been used in academia, having several articles published in peer-review journals (Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2007; Calvo-Alvarado *et al.* 2009).

Several studies have investigated the factors that have been driving the recent changes in land use / land cover in Costa Rica (Joyce 2006; Calvo-Alvarado *et al.* 2009; Quesada, M. & K. Stoner 2004). They note that the decrease in forest cover during the early years of the nineteenth century until the 1960s was guided by the expansion of the population centers within the country. The forest assessment in the 1960s quantified that by that time, 60 percent of the country was still covered by forest (Calvo-Alvarado 2009). Later, due to economic factors driven by the international markets and their influence in the agricultural policies of the country, Costa Rica suffered a sudden increase in the

deforestation rate, having its peak during the 1980s when only 41 percent of the country was covered by forest (Arroyo-Mora, Sánchez-Azofeifa, Rivard *et al.* 2005; Calvo-Alvarado 2009). During the early years of the 1990s, new changes in political and social factors affected the country and were reflected in an overall increase of the forest cover. This recovery is still taking place, having currently 48 percent of country covered by forest (Calvo-Alvarado 2009). Calvo *et al.* (2009) and Arroyo *et al.* (2005) link these fluctuations to the international beef prices and show in their articles a strong correlation between average beef prices in the United States and the amount of forest cover in Costa Rica. Calvo (2009) notes that the increase in forest cover of the last twenty years is not only related to low beef prices, but also to the establishment of tourism as a main industry, intensification of the agricultural techniques, shifts in rural communities toward a more urban lifestyle and new laws and economic incentives for conservation.

The effectiveness of the conservation areas in protecting the different ecosystems of Costa Rica was first addressed by a study called *Proyecto GRUAS* (García 1996). It was the first to employ a gap analysis method (Scott *et al.* 1993) by using vegetation maps as an approximation of the biodiversity in the country. This study resulted in a conservation strategy with the goal of protecting 90 percent of the different vegetation associations through a network of National Parks and privately funded reserves. Powell *et al.* (2000) did a similar analysis,

but instead of vegetation maps, they used biodiversity maps based on the Holdridge Life Zones System (Holdridge 1967). Their results show that for the 23 different Life Zones in Costa Rica, only nine of them were adequately protected by the conservation areas that existed at that time. Two other studies using a similar gap analysis approach were published during the last two years. The first one by Kohlmann *et al.* (2007) used dung beetle geographic distributions based on the Holdridge Life Zones maps. Similar to the findings of the other two studies, they concluded that the protected areas do not coincide with the areas of high species richness and endemism of the studied species. Finally, during the last year, the second part of the *Proyecto GRUAS* was published (Arias *et al.* 2008). It used a new map of vegetation associations created by Zamora (2008), which according to the authors is an overall improvement over the Holdridge Life Zones and the vegetation classification used by Garcia (1996). The results of *GRUAS 2* are currently used as a base map for creating connectivity routes between the protected areas of the country.

In summary, this literature review shows that there is empirical evidence of the negative effects that habitat fragmentation has on biodiversity, especially on species of tropical trees. It also gives some insights into the considerations and theory behind SDMs and shows that there is a lack of studies employing SDMs in the tropics, an attractive area of research due to its proved ability for addressing

conservation questions. Finally, it gives a short overview of the research that has been carried out in Costa Rica in terms of biodiversity mapping and conservation effectiveness.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The following paragraphs describe the methodology used to address the three main questions of this project: (a) how much of the species' original suitable habitat has been affected by Land-Use / Land-Cover Change, (b) how much of the remaining habitat is inside protected areas, and (c) how fragmented is the unprotected habitat within the study area in Costa Rica.

Study area

This study evaluates timber trees within Costa Rica, covering the entire 51,000 km² area of the country (Figure 1). Costa Rica is located between 7° - 11° N latitude and 83° - 85° W longitude, and is bordered by the countries of Nicaragua and Panama to north and south, respectively; and the Pacific Ocean and the Atlantic Ocean to the west and east, respectively. Three main mountain ranges cross the country trending NW to SE, reaching a maximum elevation of 3,821 meters. Due to its geographic position between the North and South American continents and the wide range of microclimates, the country has been known for its high biodiversity. It is estimated that more than 2,000 species of trees are found in its forests (Jiménez-Madrigal 1998).

Figure 1. Map of Costa Rica showing topography and protected areas (source: *Atlas Digital de Costa Rica 2008*)

Mean annual temperatures in Costa Rica range from 32° C in the Pacific coast to 2.2° C at the highest peak (Janzen 1983). The country has a dry and wet season driven by the northeast trade winds, the seasonal shifts of the eastern

Pacific Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), the cold continental outbreaks and the influence of tropical cyclones in the Caribbean coast (Waylen, Caviedes, & Quesada 1996). Precipitation has two peaks, the first one usually occurs during May-June and the second in October. Annual precipitation ranges between 1,400 mm in the NW coast and 8,500 mm in the mountains of the middle of the country (Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica 2008).

Forest currently covers 48 percent of the extent of the country, of which 31 percent is protected in National Parks and other protected areas, leaving close to 10 percent with potential for managed forestry. The area with potential for managed forestry is widespread throughout the countryside in small forest patches (Quesada 2007; Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2003; Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2001). Since 1997, the Costa Rican government has been protecting 18 species of trees used for timber, supporting this measure with Forest Law #7575, which prohibits forest cover change and starts a payment for ecosystem services (PES) program (Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2007). According to two studies of land-cover change in 2000 and 2005, these measures have helped in reducing the overall rate of deforestation in the country (Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2007, 2006).

Selected species

This study evaluates 29 timber species used in Costa Rica (Table 1). This group of species is part of an original list of 60 species of potential interest created based on suggestions from Costa Rican foresters and two books about native Costa Rican trees used as timber: *Arboles del Trópico Húmedo. Importancia socioeconómica* (Flores-Vindas & Obando-Vargas 2003) and *Arboles Maderables en Peligro de Extinción* (Jiménez-Madrigal 1998). Of the original list, 31 species were eliminated due to small number of samples and model evaluations, discussed later in the methodology.

The selected species are native to Costa Rica, highly associated with old-growth forests, economically valuable, and due to their slow growth (and problems of pests in g. *Swietenia* and g. *Cedrela*) are not attractive for commercial tree plantations. These characteristics make these species prone to overexploitation by timber industries in the remaining forest fragments where the species persist. Eight of the selected species are currently protected by Costa Rican law and were used as a guide to compare the habitat fragmentation of the other species and suggest possible management actions.

Table 1. Species and the number of different localities used in the analyses.

Species	Code	Family	Different Localities
<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i> *	An choc	Caryocaraceae	10
<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	As grav	Anacardiaceae	15
<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	Bo quin	Malvaceae	15
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	Ca bras	Clusiaceae	18
<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	Ca cost	Caryocaraceae	19
<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i> *	Ca burg	Lauraceae	13
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	Ce odor	Meliaceae	12
<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	Ce tond	Meliaceae	12
<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	Co guia	Lecythidaceae	13
<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	Cy hemi	Caesalpiniaceae	9
<i>Dalbergia retusa</i> *	Da retu	Fabaceae	18
<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	Du macr	Fabaceae	12
<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i> *	Gu sanc	Zygophyllaceae	17
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	Hu digu	Humiriaceae	21
<i>Minquartia guianensis</i>	Mi guia	Olacaceae	21
<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	Or pter	Juglandaceae	9
<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	Pe purp	Caesalpiniaceae	12
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	Pe macr	Fabaceae	13
<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i> *	Pl parv	Fabaceae	9
<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i> *	Pl pinn	Fabaceae	9
<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i> *	Po guat	Podocarpaceae	11
<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	Pr copa	Fabaceae	9
<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	Qu seem	Fagaceae	40
<i>Samanea saman</i>	Sa sama	Fabaceae	17
<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	Si capi	Sapotaceae	17
<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	St micr	Fabaceae	13
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i> *	Sw macr	Meliaceae	15
<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	Ta guay	Bignoniaceae	9
<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	Va barb	Humiriaceae	9
Total			417

*Species currently protected by law

Habitat suitability modeling

Localities

The coordinates where the species were found (localities) were obtained from the database of the herbarium at the *Instituto Nacional de Biodiversidad* (INBio) in Costa Rica. Each of the localities is associated with specimens that were identified by the herbarium personnel. The total of 417 localities used in this study are spread across the whole country and were collected between 1986 and 2006 (Fig 2). The coordinates were assigned by collectors using the current Costa Rican topographic maps (scale 1:50,000) and Geographic Positioning Systems (GPSs). All localities are in geographic coordinates and based on the WGS84 datum. Each of the studied species has more than nine different localities, a number considered adequate for producing good species distribution models – suitable habitat maps (Hernandez *et al.* 2006; Pearson *et al.* 2007).

Figure 2. Localities of tree species used in the modeling. (Source: INBio and *Atlas Digital de Costa Rica 2008*)

Environmental layers

Species distribution models (SDMs) were created using 20 environmental layers (Table 2) including the soils map of Costa Rica (Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica 2008) and 19 bioclimatic variables that are part of the Worldclim 1.4

interpolated environmental layers (Hijmans *et al.* 2005). The soils map was digitized by the Tropical Science Center in Costa Rica from 1:200,000 maps created in 1989 as part of Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) soils mapping project and was available in digital form as part of the Costa Rican Digital Atlas (Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica 2008). It contains 75 soil great groups based on the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) soils classification system. The soils layer was converted into a raster file using a cell size of 30 arcseconds (\approx 1km). This is the same size of the Worldclim dataset, the coarsest resolution of the layers used.

According to the climatic stations datasets used by Worldclim (Hijmans *et al.* 2005), the layers for Costa Rica were interpolated based on at least 10 years of data from 132 precipitation stations and 47 temperature stations located inside the country (Figure 2). These bioclimatic layers are commonly used in species distribution modeling because they represent more biological meaningful variables than the original monthly precipitation and temperature layers (Nix 1986).

Table 2. Environmental layers used to create the species distribution models

	Variable	Units	Source
1	Annual Mean Temperature	°C	Worldclim
2	Mean Diurnal Range	°C	Worldclim
3	Isothermality	°C x 100	Worldclim
4	Temperature Seasonality	%	Worldclim
5	Max Temperature of Warmest Month	°C	Worldclim
6	Min Temperature of Coldest Month	°C	Worldclim
7	Temperature Annual Range	°C	Worldclim
8	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	°C	Worldclim
9	Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	°C	Worldclim
10	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	°C	Worldclim
11	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	°C	Worldclim
12	Annual Precipitation	mm	Worldclim
13	Precipitation of Wettest Month	mm	Worldclim
14	Precipitation of Driest Month	mm	Worldclim
15	Precipitation Seasonality	%	Worldclim
16	Precipitation of Wettest Quarter	mm	Worldclim
17	Precipitation of Driest Quarter	mm	Worldclim
18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	mm	Worldclim
19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	mm	Worldclim
20	Soils	Great Groups USDA system	Atlas Costa Rica

Figure 3. Weather stations with more than 10 years of climatic data used by Worldclim in Costa Rica and parts of Nicaragua and Panama (sources: Global Historical Climatology Network and FAO).

Modeling technique

Models were created using Maxent version 3.3.1. Maxent is a machine learning algorithm based on the principle of maximum entropy used to model species distributions. It operates by assuming that the presence data of the

species are taken from an unknown probability distribution, and estimates this distribution using a set of constraints called *features* created with the environmental layers of the study area (Phillips *et al.* 2006). Maxent uses the presence data to calculate the empirical values of these *features*, and finds the probability distribution of maximum entropy (closest to uniform) that matches their empirical average (Phillips *et al.* 2006). This probability distribution is based only on the environmental conditions of the study area, and due to computational limitations of including all the cells of the environmental layers in the modeling, they are sampled using a set of *background points* spread across the area. The selection of these background points has important implications in the performance of the models (Phillips & Dudik 2008). Following the recommendations of Phillips *et al.* (2009) and Phillips & Dudik (2008), presence points were included in the background and a total of 10,000 background points were used as a way to reduce the sample selection bias and improve the overall performance of the model.

Maxent was chosen as the modeling technique because several studies consider it one of the best methods to model species distributions when presence-only data and small number of localities are used (Elith *et al.* 2006; Hernandez *et al.* 2006; Phillips *et al.* 2006; Wisz *et al.* 2008; Elith & Graham 2009) and also because it has the capability of using both categorical variables

(e.g. soils layer) and continuous variables (e.g. bioclimatic layers). The outputs given by Maxent are raster files where each cell has a probability value of suitable habitat, hereafter called suitable habitat layers.

The modeling methodology was based on a study by Kremen *et al.* (2008). The list of species were divided into two groups based on their number of localities: for each species with more than 11 different localities, a total of 100 models were created by sampling with replacement (bootstrapping), randomly selecting 75 percent of the localities for creating the model and the other 25 percent for evaluating it. For species with fewer localities, the actual number of training and testing combinations was used. A final suitable habitat map of each species was created by averaging all its models. This method is considered a good way for creating species distribution models using a small number of localities (Pearson *et al.* 2007).

The models were evaluated using the Area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC), a measure widely used to assess the performance of species distribution models (Fielding & Bell 1997; Phillips *et al.* 2006). AUC is a threshold-independent evaluation method with values ranging from zero to one; one being a model that discriminates perfectly between cells where the species is known to be present and absent, 0.5 representing a model that did not

perform better than a random prediction, and less than 0.5 indicating models that performed worst than random predictions (Elith *et al.* 2006). In cases such as this study, where the true absences are unknown, the AUC is defined as the probability of the model to differentiate between a presence cell (locality) and a random cell of the study area (Phillips *et al.* 2009). Following the methodology used in Kremen *et al.* (2008), an AUC was calculated for each of the models of each species, and the species was selected for the next section of the study if the lower 95% confidence limit of the AUC distribution was greater than 0.5.

The probability values of the average models were transformed into layers of presence-absence of suitable habitat using as a threshold the lowest probability value of the observed localities of each species. A particular cell was considered suitable habitat for a species if that cell was at least as suitable as the cells where the species was recorded, an approach previously used by Phillips *et al.* (2006) and Pearson *et al.* (2007). All the resulting distribution maps were revised with the available biogeographic literature of the species in Costa Rica, an overall process that reduced the original list of 60 species to the 29 species used in the study.

Current Suitable Habitat

Current suitable habitat (CSH) refers to the areas of the modeled suitable habitat that are currently forest. These cells were identified using the Forest Cover dataset created by Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* (2006) with remotely sensed data from year 2005. This forest cover was created as part of the Payment for Ecosystem Services Program of the *Fondo de Financiamiento Forestal* (FONAFIFO) and followed a methodology established in an earlier forest assessment (Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2001). In their classification, forests are areas greater than 1 ha with a canopy density of 80 percent or greater, excluding native forests in an early successional state, tree plantations and agroforestry systems. This layer is available as a vector file and therefore was converted into a raster layer using the same cell size ($\approx 1 \text{ km}^2$) of all the previously created rasters. The transformation was done by assigning a forest or non-forest value to each cell according to which of the two land covers had the largest area within that cell ('maximum-area' option in ArcGIS). This process resulted in new layers of current suitable habitat for each of the species.

Landscape analysis

First, the suitable habitat layers were projected into the Costa Rica Transverse Mercator (CRTM) coordinate system using cells of 1km x 1km (100

ha). Then, the following areas were calculated for each species: total suitable habitat (not considering forest cover), current suitable habitat (considering forest cover) and current suitable habitat inside and outside the protected areas of the country. The protected areas are based on a GIS layer that is part of the Digital Atlas of Costa Rica (Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica 2008); it was created by the *Sistema Nacional de Areas de Conservacion* (SINAC) and shows areas with different degrees of logging protection (e.g. National Parks, Biological Reserves, Indigenous Territories and Wildlife Refuges).

Fragmentation of current suitable habitat outside protected areas was assessed with Fragstats 3.3 (McGarigal *et al.* 2002) using four landscape metrics. Patch area and its total area were used to account for the amount of habitat, Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (NND) between patches for spatial isolation, and fractal dimension index (FDI) to account for the possible edge effects affecting the patches. The relationship between area, amount of habitat, NDD and spatial isolation is straightforward, but between FDI and edge needs some clarification. FDI is a widely used landscape metric that measures the irregularity of the edge of a patch based on a relationship between area and perimeter (Lovejoy 1982). Its value is independent of the size of the patch and ranges between one and two, one being a simple circular patch and higher values indicating more complex shapes (Krummel *et al.* 1987). Complex shapes

have a higher edge-to-interior ratio than simpler ones, meaning that patches with complex shapes are more affected by edge effects than patches with simpler shapes.

The species were ranked separately by their total CSH and the 90th percentile of their patch area, NDD and FDI respectively. The 90th percentile was chosen instead of measures of central tendency because the distribution of the variables is positively skewed, with most of the records having the lowest values measured (especially patch area and NDD, this can be seen in Appendix B). Due to this skewness, ranking using median or lower percentiles would result in several species having the same rank and in being unable to differentiate the fragmentation between them.

The ranking was done by giving lower ranks to the values that represent higher fragmentation (i.e. smaller total unprotected CSH, smaller patch area, higher FDI and higher NND). For each species, the four different ranks were added to calculate a general fragmentation rank. The general fragmentation rank weighted all the variables the same due to lack of research showing the specific effects that they have on each of the species. To avoid redundancy among the variables in the calculation of the general fragmentation rank, a Spearman's correlation coefficient was calculated to ensure their low correlation.

The analyses were carried out using ArcGIS 9.3 for all the spatial analysis and spatial data preparation, R and Microsoft Excel for statistical analyses and tabular data preparation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion section is subdivided into three main topics: the landscape analysis answering the three main questions of this study; management considerations, comparing the results with other studies that used a similar methodology done in the area; and finally some methodological and ecological considerations.

Landscape analysis

Reduction in suitable habitat due to Land-Use and Land-Cover Change

The total areas of modeled habitat are shown in Figure 4. Results show that there are considerable differences in the extents of suitable habitat of each species and also in the effects that Land-Use / Land-Cover Change (LULCC) had on them. In terms of total suitable habitat, i.e. the suitable habitat in the country without taking into account the current forest extent, 25 of the 29 species studied (86 percent) have less than one million hectares (10,000 km²). Total suitable habitat areas range from 309,100 ha (6 percent of the country) to 2,526,000 ha (49 percent of the country). *Caryocar costaricense* and *Platymiscium parviflorum*

are the two species with areas smaller than 350,000 ha, while *Astronium gravelones* and *Bombacopsis quinata* are the two with areas greater than 2,000,000 ha.

As shown in Figure 5, LULCC reduced the suitable habitat of each species in different amounts. Percentages range from 31 percent for *Dussia macrophyllata* to 74 percent for *Platymiscium parviflorum*. Eleven species have less than half of its predicted total suitable habitat covered by forest; four of these species are protected by law (*Platymiscium parviflorum*, *Guaiacum sanctum*, *Swietenia macrophylla* & *Dalbergia retusa*). Comparing Figure 4 and 5, it is clear that the proportion of remaining suitable habitat is not correlated with the total suitable habitat of the species (Spearman's correlation coefficient = -0.39). In other words, LULLC affected the studied species in different amounts despite their different original habitat size.

Figure 4. Total and current areas of modeled suitable habitat. (* species currently protected by law). See Table 1 for key to species names.

Figure 5. Reduction in suitable habitat due to land-use / land-cover change (* species currently protected by law)

Suitable habitat under protection

Total areas of protected and unprotected current suitable habitat (CSH) are presented in Figure 6. CSH areas range from 86,100 ha (1.7 percent of the country) of *Platymiscium parviflorum* to 868,700 ha (17 percent of the country) of *Bombacopsis quinata*. It is clear that there are differences between species in the amounts of CSH protected (Figure 6). To make these differences more evident, Figure 7 shows the proportion of their CSH unprotected. It ranges from ten percent for *Cedrela tonduzii* to 77 percent for *Swietenia macrophylla*. It is important to note that seven species have more than half of its CSH unprotected (i.e. *Swietenia macrophylla*, *Guaiacum sanctum*, *Platymiscium parviflorum*, *Bombacopsis quinata*, *Sideroxylon capiri*, *Samanea saman*, *Dalbergia retusa*), and three of those are species that are not currently protected by law (i.e. *Bombacopsis quinata*, *Sideroxylon capiri* and *Samanea saman*). It is also evident that there is no correlation between the amount of CSH and its proportion unprotected (Spearman's correlation coefficient = -0.14), meaning that the degree of protection of the species is not related to the size of their current habitat.

Figure 6. Total areas of protected and unprotected current suitable habitat. (* species currently protected by law)

Figure 7. Proportion of current suitable habitat in unprotected areas. (* species currently protected by law)

Fragmentation of the unprotected habitat

Table 3 shows the four landscape variables (CSH, patch area, NDD, FDI) and the values used to rank the fragmentation of unprotected CSH of the species. The influence of each of the variables evaluated is shown in Figures 8, 9 and 10. As previously noted in the methods, these figures represent the 90th percentile of CSH of the patches, NND between patches and FDI respectively. The four variables were slightly correlated, having the highest correlation between FDI and patch area (Spearman's correlation coefficient = 0.67, p-value < 0.01, see also Appendix D). The general fragmentation rank, calculated with the totals of the ranks of each species, is shown in Table 3 and Figure 11. In terms of the ten most fragmented species outside of the protected areas, only *Platymiscium parviflorum* is protected by law. Considering the ten least fragmented species, *Podocarpus guatemalensis* and *Swietenia macrophylla* are the only two species protected by law.

Figure 8. 90th percentile of fractal dimension index of unprotected patches of current suitable habitat. Higher values represent more complex shapes. (* species currently protected by law)

Figure 9. 90th percentile of the areas of unprotected patches of current suitable habitat. (* species currently protected by law)

Figure 10. 90th percentile of nearest-neighbor distance between current suitable habitat patches. (* species currently protected by law)

Table 3. Values and ranks of unprotected CSH. The five most fragmented species are shown in bold.

Species	CSH	90 th percentile			Ranks	Fragmentation
	unprotected	Patch Area	NND	FDI	total	rank
<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i> *	68,000 (4)	2,430 (25)	4,332.52 (12)	1.0889 (8)	45	10
<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	394,900 (28)	1,610 (14)	4,098.48 (16)	1.0810 (17)	47	19
<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	475,200 (29)	1,600 (13)	3,605.55 (19)	1.0830 (15)	47	20
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	150,600 (19)	1,690 (16)	4,123.11 (15)	1.0754 (22)	53	18
<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	86,000 (9)	1,700 (17)	6,531.13 (2)	1.0902 (6)	25	2
<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i> *	134,900 (15)	1,510 (11)	4,472.14 (11)	1.0814 (16)	38	11
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	321,100 (27)	1,400 (8)	4,242.64 (13)	1.0779 (20)	41	16
<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	26,900 (1)	500 (1)	5,385.17 (5)	1.0581 (27)	33	2
<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	117,500 (12)	1,600 (13)	5,545.29 (4)	1.0860 (11)	28	5
<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	140,900 (16)	1,730 (18)	4,788.85 (9)	1.0926 (1)	28	8
<i>Dalbergia retusa</i> *	126,900 (14)	1,200 (6)	5,300.00 (6)	1.0795 (19)	31	9
<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	74,700 (6)	1,650 (15)	3,960.56 (18)	1.0832 (14)	47	11
<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i> *	154,400 (20)	1,470 (10)	4,182.87 (14)	1.0886 (9)	33	11
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	82,200 (7)	1,700 (17)	5,154.07 (7)	1.0872 (10)	34	6
<i>Minuartia guianensis</i>	88,900 (10)	1,610 (14)	4,472.14 (11)	1.0898 (7)	32	7
<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	144,100 (17)	2,340 (24)	4,683.28 (10)	1.0903 (4)	38	12
<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	85,300 (8)	1,890 (19)	7,071.07 (1)	1.0911 (3)	23	1
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	197,800 (23)	2,060 (22)	3,605.55 (19)	1.0852 (12)	53	20
<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i> *	45,100 (2)	650 (2)	5,000.00 (8)	1.0674 (26)	36	4
<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i> *	155,000 (21)	2,050 (21)	5,385.17 (5)	1.0837 (13)	39	13
<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i> *	209,100 (24)	1,700 (17)	5,000.00 (8)	1.0809 (18)	43	15
<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	71,200 (5)	870 (3)	5,385.17 (5)	1.0749 (24)	32	3
<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	160,500 (22)	2,150 (23)	3,605.55 (19)	1.0902 (5)	47	17
<i>Samanea saman</i>	150,300 (18)	1,090 (5)	4,123.11 (15)	1.0751 (23)	43	14
<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	122,700 (13)	1,030 (4)	4,472.14 (11)	1.0678 (25)	40	11
<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	224,000 (25)	1,520 (12)	4,000.00 (17)	1.0762 (21)	50	19
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i> *	226,200 (26)	1,300 (7)	4,123.11 (15)	1.0749 (24)	46	18
<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	99,000 (11)	2,000 (20)	5,346.65 (8)	1.0914 (2)	30	6
<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	64,800 (3)	1,440 (9)	6,057.58 (3)	1.0751 (23)	35	4
Total different ranks	29	25	19	27		20

*Species currently protected by law (n) rank

Figure 11. Fragmentation index of unprotected patches of suitable habitat. Lower values represent higher fragmentation. (* species currently protected by law)

Management implications

The previous section showed that the studied species have been affected in different ways and amounts, despite their protection status or the original geographic range of their suitable habitat. How these results can help in assessing the species' risk and in developing management actions are discussed in this section using as comparison similar studies and guidelines noted in the literature. Reduction in suitable habitat, current suitable habitat and its protected amount will be addressed by comparing the results with thresholds given by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red Book (IUCN 2001)

and gap analyses done in Costa Rica (Powell *et al.* 2000; Arias *et al.* 2008). The fragmentation of the unprotected habitat is discussed focusing on the most fragmented species.

As previously noted, the reduction of suitable habitat is different for each of the studied species, and this reduction can be seen as a proxy for the decrease of the species' original geographic range (Arroyo *et al.* 2009). The reduction of the species' habitat reflects a long history of deforestation. The literature available about the land-use / land-cover history of Costa Rica note clearly that deforestation and its drivers has varied in each different region of the country (Arroyo-Mora *et al.* 2005; Joyce 2006; Sánchez-Azofeifa *et al.* 2003). As the geographic ranges of the studied species are spread throughout the country, the fluctuating degree of deforestation per region noted by the aforementioned articles describe the varied reasons the studied species have been affected in differing amounts.

One way to classify the reduction of the species habitat is given by the IUCN in its Red List Categories and Criteria (IUCN 2001), a methodology previously applied in Mexico with maps of suitable habitat created using SDMs (Arroyo *et al.* 2009). The IUCN methodology uses differing thresholds for various criteria to classify the degree of endangerment to a species and includes nine different categories. The categories of threatened species range from *least*

concern, vulnerable, endangered and critically endangered, and represent increasing risks of extinction, respectively.

Taking into account the reduction in suitable habitat (see Figure 5) the studied species fall in two of the IUCN categories. For this criterion, IUCN Red Book uses 70 percent of habitat reduction as the threshold to separate between *vulnerable* and *endangered* categories. According to the percentages of suitable habitat reduction, *Platymiscium parviflorum* and *Guaiacum sanctum* fall in the *endangered species* category while all the other subject species fall into the *vulnerable* category. Even though the current Costa Rican Forest Legislation was not based on the IUCN methodology (de Grammont & Cuarón 2006) in the case of this criterion, it already protects the two most threatened species by banning their logging.

Current suitable habitat (see Figure 4), a proxy for the species' current range, can be analyzed using thresholds also given by the IUCN methodology. In this case, the value separating the categories of *vulnerable* and *least concern* is an area of 200,000 ha. Using this threshold, *Platymiscium parviflorum*, *Dalbergia retusa* and *Prioria copaifera* fall into the category of *vulnerable species* while the remaining species fall under the category of *least concern*. Of the three *vulnerable* species, only *Prioria copaifera* is not protected by law. Even though the risk of the species in this criterion is lower than in the habitat reduction

criterion, the Forest Law seems to be protecting the species that are at higher risk.

In terms of the amount of the species range inside protected areas, the gap analyses made in Costa Rica give values to assess their degree of protection (see Appendix E for actual maps). Powell *et al.* (2000) and Arias *et al.* (2008) used a threshold of 100 km² (10,000 ha) of habitat inside protected areas to classify an ecologic community adequately protected. According to this threshold and the values presented in Figure 6, even *Platymiscium parviflorum*, which is the species with the smallest amount of current suitable habitat protected (41,000 ha), would be considered adequately protected from a management point of view.

According to the results discussed above, it may seem that the Forest Law in Costa Rica is protecting the most threatened timber species, but it is important to note that only a fraction of all the species logged in the country are represented in this study. The 29 species studied were modeled due to the data availability at the INBio Herbarium, excluding 31 species on the original list that did not have enough information to produce adequate models. The effect of the Forest Law in protecting the most threatened timber species will not be completely known until similar studies are performed encompassing all the species logged in the country.

The fragmentation of the species' current suitable habitat outside the protected areas can be seen as an important criterion to evaluate the long-term viability of logging in different regions of the country. Even though the current logging operations in Costa Rica are driven by principles of sustainability, the effects of historical logging (e.g. reducing population size) and the fragmentation of their unprotected range may be negatively affecting the survival of the timber species. In the last point, the quantification of the fragmentation of the species' suitable habitat is an approach capable of assessing one issue of their current status.

Despite the fact that the results mentioned above show that all the species appear adequately protected, when the unprotected current suitable habitat is considered, only one of the ten most fragmented species has been banned from logging by the Costa Rican law (see Figure 11). Going further to the five most fragmented species, none are protected from logging. Of these five species, it is interesting to note that *Peltogyne purpurea*, *Caryocar costaricense* and *Vantanea barbourii* are located mainly around the Osa Peninsula, in the South Pacific Coast of Costa Rica (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Areas where *Peltogyne purpurea*, *Caryocar costaricense* and *Vantanea barbourii* share current suitable habitat. These are three of the most fragmented species outside the protected areas of Costa Rica.

An efficient way to allocate the limited resources available for monitoring the long-term viability of forestry operations in Costa Rica would be to focus on the most threatened species. By guiding funds to the species at higher risk, it will be possible to gather higher quality data on the actual status of these species.

Having three of the five most fragmented species located in the same region should be seen as an opportunity to study them in higher detail, designing projects to answer questions related to the fields of forestry management, population and landscape ecology. In this case, it is possible to note the usefulness of this project in guiding research for the adequate management of the Costa Rican forests. Using habitat suitability maps and landscape analyses it is possible to direct fine-scale research on the most fragmented species and identify areas in the field where these studies should be carried out.

Data quality and ecological considerations

Two important points should be taken into consideration when the created suitable habitat maps are analyzed: a) the quality and number of localities, and b) the quality of the environmental layers used. The number and quality of the localities are related to the way they sample the environmental conditions where the species can survive, i.e. its ecological niche. It is important to mention this issue due to the relatively small number of localities used to create the suitable habitat maps. The implications of not sampling the ecological niche of the species in its entirety will be reflected in maps that do not represent the actual suitable habitat of the species (Menke *et al.* 2009).

It is also important to keep in mind that the localities dataset employed is taken from a botanical collection. It may be biased due to the common way of collecting botanical specimens, preferring places of easy access (e.g. forested areas around towns, rivers or roads) than using an established sampling technique (Phillips *et al.* 2009). If these situations occur, the maps will be restricted only to the environmental conditions similar to where the species were collected, leaving out areas of different climatic conditions suitable for the species that have not yet been sampled. Without independent datasets to test the models, it is difficult to identify to what degree these issues affect the suitable maps. Assuming that they occur, their influence will be reflected in maps that underpredict the suitable habitat of the species, making this study a conservative analysis of the species status.

The second issue mentioned before is related to the environmental variables used in the modeling, which in this case are the bioclimatic and soils layers. The Worldclim bioclimatic layers are based on spatial interpolations of climatic data gathered by stations located across the world. Even though there are a considerable number of stations in Costa Rica (1 precipitation station per 387 km², 1 temperature station per 1,087 km²), it is evident from Figure 3 that the distribution of these stations is clustered in certain regions. The bioclimatic layers interpolated from the stations data may reflect in an acceptable way the general climatic conditions of the country at the 1 km cells of the Worldclim data, but their

representativeness of the microclimatic conditions will be uncertain in areas with a low number of stations. These areas with fewer stations are more evident in the southeastern side of the country, a mountainous region part of La Amistad National Park, the largest National Park in Costa Rica. Due to the low density of climatic stations and the expected differences between the actual climate and the interpolated layers, the suitable habitat modeled in this area has to be taken with caution, added to the likelihood that mountainous regions will have more detailed variability of climate. It is also likely that the climatic layers and the suitable habitat maps will be different if other spatial interpolation techniques are used, especially in the regions with few climatic stations.

The difference between suitable habitat maps and the actual species distribution is another important issue that needs to be discussed. In tree species used for timber, the reasons for this difference include not only the ecological characteristics of the species (Peterson 2003), but also human influences. This is important because the 29 studied species have been extracted from the Costa Rican forests over long periods of time, even before the forest law enforced the use of long-term silvicultural practices. This historical extraction has influenced timber species in both the number of surviving individuals and their geographic distribution. For example, forest areas where the species were originally found may already have their populations extinct due to historical logging. The methodology employed in this project is not capable of quantifying the actual

effects that historical logging have in the populations of each of the studied species, but it can be used in conjunction with field data gathered from the remaining patches of suitable habitat to serve as a baseline to assess its effects.

One example that helps illustrate the issue of historical logging is the tropical tree *Swietenia macrophylla*, a timber species included in this analysis and internationally known as Honduras mahogany. In Costa Rica its distribution is located in the north west of the country (Figure 13), a region affected by deforestation due to cattle grazing and timber extraction since the 16th century (Céspedes *et al.* 2003). At that time, the logging approach was to extract only the highest value trees, and mahogany was one of the species most affected, ending up almost extinct in the country (Jiménez-Madrigal 1998). Even though mahogany is currently protected by law in Costa Rica, its recovery is slow and trees may not be present in many areas that were part of its original distribution. In cases like mahogany, where species have been logged for extended periods of time, differences are expected between the maps of suitable habitat and the actual species distribution. The uncertainty of these differences should be considered when suitable habitat maps are used in forest management, remarking the importance of field studies as the best way to assess the species' current status.

Figure 13. Current suitable habitat of *Swietenia macrophylla* and the protected areas in Costa Rica.

As noted in the mahogany example, population size is not necessarily related to the extent of its suitable habitat, and this relationship may also be different for each species. It is important to keep in mind these differences when the amounts of suitable habitat are compared between species because fragmentation effects, which take place at the population level, may not be

reflected in the amounts of area of suitable habitat for the species. In other words, species with large amounts of suitable habitat do not necessarily have a larger population size than species with smaller suitable habitat. As this relationship between areas and population size is unknown, the comparisons of habitat fragmentation between species done in the analysis may still be uncertain at the population level.

Another important subject is the ecological effect of habitat fragmentation at the studied scale. As previously noted in the methods section, this analysis was done using the cell size of the lowest resolution data (100 ha cells). According to the literature available, it is still not known if this cell size is able to encompass the effects of habitat fragmentation. The research done at the Biological Dynamics of Forest Fragments Project in Brazil previously mentioned in the literature review (i.e. Laurance *et al.* 1998, 2000, 2002, 2006), suggest that the most significant effects of habitat fragmentation occur in forest patches smaller than 100 ha. The degree to which these effects take place in larger patches of tropical forests is still not well documented nor the actual significance of each of the landscape variables at the current scale.

The final point related to the scale of the analysis is that, even though researchers noted that the overall effects of fragmentation are negative for tropical trees associated with old-growth forests, it seems that the degree to

which fragmentation affects them is specific for each species and the landscape analyzed. These specific effects have been studied only for few species and at a scale finer than the current study, measuring the influence in individual trees (e.g. Cascante *et al.* 2002; Fuchs *et al.* 2003; Quesada *et al.* 2004). The response of the species to the different land-uses/land-covers in which the landscape is configured should be considered for future studies. This is important to keep in mind due to possible effects of land uses favorable to biodiversity, which may benefit tree species by increasing seed dispersal and movement of pollination vectors between trees and forest patches (Pejchar *et al.* 2008).

All the mentioned issues may suggest that habitat suitability mapping has limitations when used to assess habitat fragmentation of timber species, but due to the limitations of information currently available about the species ecology, the costs of doing more specific studies of each species, the urgency of conservation actions in threatened forests, and the large amount of data from museum collections available online that can be used with this technique, the current approach is a method that can answer one aspect of a bigger conservation question. In the case of Costa Rica, a country with a large amount of data available at the INBio and National Herbariums (Cayuela *et al.* 2009), it is possible to apply this methodology to different species or taxonomic groups. It has already been noted in other studies (Powell *et al.* 2000; Arias *et al.* 2008) that SDMs of groups of species reflect the biodiversity of an area in a more

realistic way than what was done in previous studies using vegetation associations and bioclimatic maps (e.g. Holdridge's Life Zones).

Even though similar techniques have been used in other tropical countries, especially in Mexico (Solano & Feria 2007; Arroyo *et al.* 2009; Illoldi-Rangel, Sánchez-Cordero, & Townsend Peterson 2004; Ortega-Huerta & Peterson 2004), this project is the first study in Costa Rica using SDMs to assess the fragmentation status of a group of species. Another important aspect of this study is that it can still be adjusted using finer data, interpolating the climatic datasets with other techniques, generating higher resolution climatic surfaces and using presence data from forest plots. This can be done in combination with field studies to identify the forest patches or regions where the species are not present, estimate densities in patches where the species are found and assess the actual size of their populations. It also has the potential of helping in the selection of areas apt for restoration plans and guiding in better forest management practices.

CONCLUSIONS

This project shows that, even though there are several considerations that have to be taken into account when using species distribution modeling, the technique can be used in conjunction with landscape analysis to assess several issues of habitat fragmentation and conservation status of a group of timber species. In this project it was possible to investigate how deforestation affected the geographic range of 29 timber species in Costa Rica, assessing their degree of protection and the fragmentation of their range outside the protected areas of the country.

Throughout this study, it was possible to identify that the geographic range of the studied species has been affected by deforestation in different amounts. The reduction of their habitat is disproportional to the original extent of their range and *Platymiscium parviflorum* and *Guaiacum sanctum*, the two most threatened species according to guidelines established by IUCN, are currently protected by Costa Rican law by banning their logging.

The current habitat of the studied species is also protected in different amounts, and these amounts are not proportional to the species' current range. Using the guidelines given by the IUCN Red List, the species with the smallest

range fall into the *vulnerable* category. According to the guidelines given by previous studies that assessed the representativeness of ecosystems in the protected areas of the country (gap analyses) all the studied species are considered adequately protected.

The degree of fragmentation of the species' range outside protected areas is different for each species; unprotected species (species that are not banned) are the ones with more fragmented distributions. Of the five most fragmented species, *Peltogyne purpurea*, *Caryocar costaricense* and *Vantanea barbourii* are located in the same region, the Osa Peninsula. Due to the necessity to focus the limited resources available for conservation in the most threatened species, the situation of having these three species located in the same area can be seen as an opportunity to monitor their actual fragmentation and the overall population status in the field.

This project shows that it is possible to address a conservation question by using data taken from natural history museums, land cover maps derived from remotely sensed images and GIS analysis. The results and discussion give important information capable of helping in the sustainable management of the Costa Rican forests by providing valuable baseline data to inform land managers and policymakers.

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Appendix A

Summary of habitat modeling

Sp ID	Species	#Training samples	Lower 95% conf. int.	Minimum training presence
1	<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i>	10	0.9478	0.2726
2	<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	15	0.7473	0.2364
3	<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	15	0.7311	0.2496
4	<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	18	0.7396	0.2457
5	<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	19	0.9256	0.2064
6	<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i>	13	0.9003	0.1483
7	<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	12	0.7160	0.2747
8	<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	12	0.9076	0.3293
9	<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	13	0.8844	0.3325
10	<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	9	0.9009	0.3797
11	<i>Dalbergia retusa</i>	18	0.9051	0.1628
12	<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	12	0.8073	0.2536
13	<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i>	17	0.8720	0.1302
14	<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	21	0.9313	0.0593
15	<i>Minuartia guianensis</i>	21	0.8891	0.2136
16	<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	9	0.8175	0.298
17	<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	12	0.9096	0.2572
18	<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	13	0.7997	0.3022
19	<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i>	9	0.7682	0.2361
20	<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i>	9	0.7216	0.3543
21	<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i>	11	0.8381	0.1998
22	<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	9	0.8773	0.307
23	<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	40	0.9135	0.0938
24	<i>Samanea saman</i>	17	0.7708	0.2083
25	<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	17	0.8121	0.2171
26	<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	13	0.7388	0.2559
27	<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	15	0.7811	0.2151
28	<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	9	0.8664	0.3967
29	<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	9	0.9242	0.3245

Appendix B

Summary of total areas

Species	Total Area (ha)		
	Total suitable habitat	Current suitable habitat	Unprotected suitable habitat
<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i>	378,100	201,600	68,000
<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	2,031,600	774,800	394,900
<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	2,526,200	868,700	475,200
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	644,500	341,000	150,600
<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	309,100	210,600	86,000
<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i>	628,700	322,500	134,900
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	1,267,100	637,300	321,100
<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	414,000	261,000	26,900
<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	555,700	248,100	117,500
<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	475,800	309,600	140,900
<i>Dalbergia retusa</i>	424,900	185,600	126,900
<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	416,800	286,700	74,700
<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i>	729,500	209,000	154,400
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	500,400	318,600	82,200
<i>Minquartia guianensis</i>	375,200	249,000	88,900
<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	637,100	358,200	144,100
<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	343,800	209,500	85,300
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	809,300	405,800	197,800
<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i>	335,200	86,100	45,100
<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i>	1,009,300	661,300	155,000
<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i>	985,800	571,600	209,100
<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	447,900	198,900	71,200
<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	1,261,000	730,700	160,500
<i>Samanea saman</i>	772,100	245,900	150,300
<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	575,600	213,400	122,700
<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	1,120,000	447,800	224,000
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	892,500	294,500	226,200
<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	404,700	238,200	99,000
<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	456,000	251,100	64,800

Appendix C

Summary of landscape metrics

Current suitable habitat (whole country)

Variable: nearest neighbor distance

Species	quantiles				n
	50%	70%	90%	100%	
<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i>	2,236	2,828	4,333	9,849	75
<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	2,236	2,828	4,098	32,388	373
<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	2,236	2,236	3,606	40,112	428
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	2,236	2,880	4,123	9,849	170
<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	2,236	3,000	6,531	29,682	46
<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i>	2,236	2,828	4,472	16,125	176
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	2,236	2,828	4,243	25,318	344
<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	2,236	2,828	5,385	33,541	96
<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	2,236	3,000	5,545	16,553	83
<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	2,000	2,710	4,789	80,654	125
<i>Dalbergia retusa</i>	2,236	2,236	5,300	32,388	138
<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	2,236	2,828	3,961	21,000	102
<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i>	2,236	2,828	4,183	11,662	226
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	2,236	2,828	5,154	128,191	117
<i>Minquartia guianensis</i>	2,000	2,532	4,472	31,241	96
<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	2,236	3,000	4,683	16,279	97
<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	2,236	2,949	7,071	38,419	62
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	2,236	2,236	3,606	110,055	132
<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i>	2,236	3,049	5,000	23,345	120
<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i>	2,236	3,000	5,385	66,708	142
<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i>	2,236	3,000	5,000	28,320	263
<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	2,236	2,828	5,385	103,740	118
<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	2,000	2,236	3,606	24,187	144
<i>Samanea saman</i>	2,236	2,828	4,123	16,492	276
<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	2,236	3,000	4,472	25,000	214
<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	2,236	2,236	4,000	13,000	324
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	2,236	2,828	4,123	14,318	266
<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	2,236	2,828	5,347	15,620	92
<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	2,828	3,606	6,058	17,088	82

Appendix C (cont)

Unprotected areas

Variable: area

Species	quantiles				n
	50%	70%	90%	100%	
<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i>	200	600	2,430	8,100	72
<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	200	500	1,610	57,800	360
<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	200	400	1,600	57,800	415
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	200	400	1,690	30,000	172
<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	300	600	1,700	26,000	75
<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i>	200	400	1,510	48,200	120
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	200	400	1,400	36,200	363
<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	200	300	500	3,200	78
<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	100	400	1,600	30,700	103
<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	200	500	1,730	28,300	128
<i>Dalbergia retusa</i>	200	400	1,200	37,200	151
<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	200	500	1,650	7,100	116
<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i>	200	400	1,470	15,800	224
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	200	400	1,700	14,400	109
<i>Minqartia guianensis</i>	200	500	1,610	15,900	120
<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	300	600	2,340	20,200	132
<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	200	500	1,890	21,700	82
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	200	400	2,060	40,500	135
<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i>	150	250	650	8,400	126
<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i>	200	400	2,050	16,000	156
<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i>	200	400	1,700	23,400	267
<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	200	210	870	16,400	124
<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	200	500	2,150	19,000	178
<i>Samanea saman</i>	200	400	1,090	17,100	282
<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	200	300	1,030	15,100	228
<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	200	300	1,520	32,100	300
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	200	400	1,300	34,900	274
<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	200	600	2,000	20,900	101
<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	100	400	1,440	11,300	95

Appendix C (cont)

Unprotected areas

Variable: Fractal Dimension Index

Species	quantiles				n
	50%	70%	90%	100%	
<i>Anthodiscus chocoensis</i>	1.0013	1.0525	1.0889	1.1492	72
<i>Astronium graveolens</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0810	1.2003	360
<i>Bombacopsis quinata</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0830	1.1984	415
<i>Calophyllum brasiliense</i>	1.0081	1.0456	1.0754	1.1717	172
<i>Caryocar costaricense</i>	1.0145	1.0487	1.0902	1.1587	75
<i>Caryodaphnopsis burgeri</i>	1.0000	1.0366	1.0814	1.1824	120
<i>Cedrela odorata</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0779	1.1861	363
<i>Cedrela tonduzii</i>	1.0081	1.0193	1.0581	1.1070	78
<i>Couratari guianensis</i>	1.0000	1.0193	1.0860	1.1719	103
<i>Cynometra hemitomophylla</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0926	1.1866	128
<i>Dalbergia retusa</i>	1.0081	1.0381	1.0795	1.1844	151
<i>Dussia macrophyllata</i>	1.0081	1.0419	1.0832	1.1170	116
<i>Guaiacum sanctum</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0886	1.1469	224
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i>	1.0000	1.0470	1.0872	1.1491	109
<i>Minquartia guianensis</i>	1.0113	1.0478	1.0898	1.1365	120
<i>Oreomunnea pterocarpa</i>	1.0193	1.0495	1.0903	1.1629	132
<i>Peltogyne purpurea</i>	1.0054	1.0472	1.0911	1.1631	82
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i>	1.0081	1.0457	1.0852	1.1950	135
<i>Platymiscium parviflorum</i>	1.0041	1.0260	1.0674	1.1500	126
<i>Platymiscium pinnatum</i>	1.0081	1.0492	1.0837	1.1608	156
<i>Podocarpus guatemalensis</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0809	1.1704	267
<i>Prioria copaifera</i>	1.0081	1.0193	1.0749	1.1676	124
<i>Quercus seemannii</i>	1.0081	1.0457	1.0902	1.1460	178
<i>Samanea saman</i>	1.0081	1.0381	1.0751	1.1383	282
<i>Sideroxylon capiri</i>	1.0081	1.0294	1.0678	1.1447	228
<i>Stryphnodendron microstachyum</i>	1.0081	1.0260	1.0762	1.1654	300
<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	1.0081	1.0478	1.0749	1.1912	274
<i>Tabebuia guayacan</i>	1.0081	1.0533	1.0914	1.1624	101
<i>Vantanea barbourii</i>	1.0000	1.0425	1.0751	1.1416	95

Appendix D

Correlation between landscape variables (Spearman's)

	90th FDI	90th NND	total unprotected CSH	90th unprotected CSH
90th FDI	1	-0.04	0.30	0.67
90th NND	-0.04	1	-0.62	-0.08
total unprotected CSH	0.30	-0.62	1	0.15
90th unprotected CSH	0.67	-0.08	0.15	1

n= 29

P-value

	90th FDI	90th NND	total unprotected CSH	90th unprotected CSH
90th FDI		0.8200	0.1152	0
90th NND	0.8200		0.0003	0.6686
total unprotected CSH	0.1152	0.0003		0.4340
90th unprotected CSH	0	0.6686	0.4340	

90th FDI: 90th percentile of the Fractal Dimension Index of patches of Current Suitable Habitat (CSH)

90th NND: 90th percentile of the Nearest Neighbor Distance between patches of CSH

90th CSH: 90th percentile of the areas of patches CSH

Appendix E
Current Suitable Habitat maps

Appendix E (cont)

Appendix E (cont)

Appendix E (cont)

Appendix E (cont)

